

THE ROLE OF FORESIGHT SESSIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECO-FORESIGHT COMPETENCE

Shomurotov Bahrom Husanovich

Senior lecturer at the "Ecology and Labor Protection" department of the Institute of Engineering
Economics in Karshi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395348>

***Abstract.** In the article, the use of foresight technology in the educational process in the development of eco-foresight competence, metoeco-foresight competency models and foresight methods used in the educational process are classified according to their function. Organization of foresight sessions, its goals and objectives, stages of foresight sessions are based on the educational process.*

***Keywords:** foresight, session, thinking, cognitive, communicative, competence, demand, supply, research boundary, future map.*

INTRODUCTION.

In the training of future specialists in higher educational institutions of the world, importance is attached to the formation of ecological culture, ecological forecasting methods, including theoretical knowledge on predicting the future and creating its scenarios based on foresight technology, as well as creating practical skills [1]. Special attention is paid to the development of eco-foresight competence in students, improvement of models of eco-foresight competence and its components and criteria, justification of its pedagogical conditions, introduction of new subjects related to eco-foresight into the educational process [2]. In the international education system, scientific and research work aimed at developing foresight competence in future specialists is being carried out based on the use of foresight technology in the educational process. In developed foreign higher education institutions, they pay attention to the training of foresight technology as a separate subject in the training of managers, economists and personnel in the service sector. Boloston University of Technology (Poland) has developed a foresight education program for management, logistics and services majors, and in Germany for urban planning, architecture, and technical majors [3]. About the methodology of foresight, students are given information about dozens of methods that are most often used in foresight projects: scanning trends, creating scenarios and strategies, Delphi, brainstorming, and expert panels. Sufficient attention is also paid to strategic initiatives, project management, innovative activities, management in a changing environment, and technology evaluation. Another important aspect of foresight is its inextricable connection with other disciplines and its implementation through the integration of statistical, micro- and macroeconomic, marketing, heuristic and social methods [4].

RESEARCH METHODS

In the process of research, the analysis of scientific and teaching-methodical literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test and foresight methods were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The quality of foresight research and the accuracy of the obtained results depend on several factors, including the correct setting of the task, the appropriateness of the research method and

analysis criteria, and the competence of the expert group. Experts are required to think creatively and deviate from the traditional worldview when identifying factors that are difficult to determine and have the characteristic of chain reproduction. The strengthening of the traditions of global instability, the constant complication of economic relations, the violation of the conditions of interdependence of technical-technological development and its environmental consequences make environmental foresight research in the global ecosystem much more complicated and the assessment of the practical importance of "Creating the Future" and "Preparing for the Future" makes it difficult [5]. Foresight methods used in the educational process are divided into types such as predictive (prediction of the future), analytical (analysis of the current situation) and creative (formulation of new ideas for the future) according to their function. Some methods of foresight can be used for various purposes, including predicting the future, analyzing and studying events and the environment, creating new ideas about the future, and formulating ideas about a set goal. Another of the widely used foresight methods in the educational process is the method of organizing "Foresight sessions" [6].

The main task of a foresight session or a foresight forum is to develop foresight competencies in students to develop innovative thinking, cognitive and communication skills, to analyze the activities of their field in the rapidly changing technological and economic environment, to predict short, medium and long-term future development. consists [7,8]. The foresight session is considered the basis of the foresight competence, and its tasks include:

Organization of a technological foresight aimed at creating a future concept of the network or specialists working in it or restructuring the existing concept.

Prediction of competencies based on technological foresight.

Development of recommendations for public policy and interested labor market organizations in a specific industry or sector, aimed at reducing the gap between supply and demand.

The plan for the organization of the foresight session should be made based on the steps indicated above. Foresight acts as a teacher moderator in the session. Under the guidance of a moderator, students create a generalized future map of a specific industry or industry. Special electronic e-cards are developed for this purpose.

Foresight is organized in the following stages:

1. Identify the field or industry (or enterprise, company and organization).
2. Determining the foresight limit
3. Create a future card
4. Forecasting tasks that can happen (fulfilled) in the short, medium and long term.
5. Presentation
6. Discussion, debate
7. Evaluation, final conclusion

The main task of organizing students' activities during the foresight session is to create a future card. The map consists mainly of the following sections: trends, legal and regulatory documents, threats and opportunities.

When forecasting based on the foresight, the time horizon can be chosen: short-term (the near future, i.e. the next 2-3 years), medium-term (the next 5 years) and long-term (at least the next 10 years). In addition, the fourth time horizon is called "black swans" and is a picture of a fantastic, imaginary development that does not know when it will happen.

After choosing a time horizon, the development in a specific area is predicted. For this, the group is divided into several small groups, and each small group presents its strategic development card. In some cases, all time horizons may be taken and each subgroup within each time horizon may present a development strategy based on its predictions.

At the end of the session, each small group presents its card, the moderator (educator) organizes questions and answers and discussions. Each small group's presentation will be scored.

CONCLUSION

In the educational process, students' methodological competence regarding foresight plays an important role in choosing foresight methods. On the basis of the analysis of scientific and educational-methodical works on the use of foresight in higher education, we recommend that future ecologists should develop eco-foresight competence in 2 ways:

1. Use of foresight methods in the teaching of specialized subjects.
2. To include foresight-related subjects, for example, the subject "Ecological foresight" in the block of elective subjects of the curriculum of the educational direction.

In general, all methods of foresight can be used in the educational process in accordance with the content of the subject, the type of training and the field of education. The main thing is that in order to ensure the long-term international competitiveness of the enterprise or company in the conditions of the market economy, it is necessary to focus on the formation and development of foresight competence in order to correctly predict its future, create a future scenario, and develop a strategic plan for achieving the goal.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimov O.D., Rakhmatov M.I., Boirov Z.R. Effects of the human biosphere and environmental problems // Problems of science. - 2019. - No. 5.- pp. 6-7.
2. Zandira M.Yu. Methodology and practical application of environmental protection: analytical review. //Industrial Economics. 2020, No. 2 (90). - P.93-115
3. The best methods and tools for foresight. URL: <https://www.venturesight.com/top-foresight-methods/>
4. Noskov I.A. Foresight of education: essence, difficulty, realities. // International student scientific bulletin. – 2022. – No. 1. URL: <https://eduherald.ru/ru/article/view?id=20866>.
5. Rakhimov O. D., Chorshanbiev Z. E. Prospects for the application of digital technologies in training the "labor protection" course //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – T. 2. – P. 34-40.
6. Verkhoturova E.V. Foresight as a tool for strategic management of innovation development. Abstract of the dissertation for the search for the academic degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences. Irkutsk State University. 2013.
7. Rakhimov O. D. 1, Otakulov Yu. Yu., Raksimova D. O. Educational foresight of the quality and effectiveness of independent education // Bulletin of Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 7. – No. 110. – P. 8.
8. Noskov I.A. Foresight of education: essence, difficulties, realities // International student scientific bulletin. -2022.-No. 1. URL: <https://yeduherald.ru/ru/article/view?id=20866>.